

InnoCampus: Mobile Entrepreneurship and Fab Lab Program for Locals and Refugees

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Abstract

A mobile fab lab can radically improve access to digital manufacturing tools in the places it travels to. It also has potential to encourage local communities, schools, universities, and businesses to support and launch makerspaces and fab labs in their own cities.

A mobile fab lab which also provides entrepreneurship training can attract a wider audience and reach a more diverse group of people wherever it travels to as well as being able to support local startups with their prototyping needs.

InnoCampus is a mobile platform in Turkey which combines a startup accelerator program with a fab lab. Its objective is to reach people in different parts of the country who do not have easy access to the programs and tools it provides. Its mobility and independence give it extraordinary flexibility in the programs and methods it uses to reach a diverse group of participants.

In this paper, we evaluate the InnoCampus as a mobile startup accelerator and Fab Lab program based on program content, methods used, the impact on participants' business and personal development by using data from interviews with InnoCampus program alumni from 3 different cities in 2017.

Keywords

Mobile, Fab Lab, entrepreneurship, refugee, startup

1 Introduction

InnoCampus is a collaborative project providing an innovation and entrepreneurship experience to entrepreneurs and makers in Turkey. Its objective is to make fab lab and startup training and tools accessible to people in different locations where these are not commonly available.

The pre-fabricated portable platform consists of 3 large size containers which can be set up and disassembled in just day (Figure 16b). The 90 m² indoor space consists of a co-working area for startup teams and events, a co-learning area for training, and 2 separate rooms for the fab lab equipment which include 3D printers, a laser cutter, a desktop CNC, Arduino kits, robotics kits, and other tools. Innofablab which is a member of the international fab lab network is used both by the startup teams in the accelerator program to build their prototypes and also makers which are not necessarily entrepreneurs. The open terrace on the top is for social gatherings and discussions.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 16: InnoCampus' prefabricated structure and assembly process (a),
InnoCampus containers structure after assembly (b).

In 2,5 years, the project which is funded by sponsors has trained 66 startup teams in its accelerator program, 24 high school startup teams in high school entrepreneurship and creativity camps, and reached 422 people through its fab lab training and makerfests in 7 different locations around the country. Starting in 2017, refugee entrepreneurs were actively invited to the programs. Three startup accelerator and fab lab programs in 2017 had both local and refugee entrepreneurs take part who are also part of this research.

3 main areas which make InnoCampus unique are:

1. The program combines entrepreneurship and fab lab training.
2. The physical structure is portable. It can be moved on three trucks and set up in different locations
3. The program is cross-discipline. As well as targeting people with different backgrounds, local and refugee entrepreneurs and makers also take part in programs together.

Within InnoCampus, the fab lab infrastructure and its trainings are integral and complementary to the startup accelerator program. All of the entrepreneurs go through the basic prototyping trainings to use the 3D printers, laser cutter, and Arduino boards. Those who need to actively build prototypes attend the advanced trainings and take mentorship from the Fab Lab team.

Locals who are not part of the accelerator program often come and attend the Fab Lab trainings and use the Fab Lab for their prototyping needs. One of the events which brings together makers in each city together and with mentors who come to support the event is the maker fest. This event takes 24 hours and separate teams receive hands-on training and work on different technologies (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Drone building team in Maker Fest İzmir.

In Turkey, there is quite limited access to startup accelerators and fab lab training outside of the city of Istanbul. 2018 Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI) ranked Turkey ranked 37 in 137 countries based on its entrepreneurial attitudes, abilities and aspiration of the local population. Turkey has relatively lower performance in the parameters of risk acceptance, competition in the market, networking and human capital (Figure 18) (Acs, Szerb, & Lloyd, 2018). Access to different forms of startup training around the country has potential to help with the development of some of these parameters. There are only 10 registered Fab Labs in Turkey, 8 of which are in Istanbul (Fab Foundation). There are also science centers in other 9 cities which provide some maker workshops for children or the youth, but they do not serve as full-fledged Fab Labs or makerspaces (Science Centers Organization, 2014; TÜBİTAK, 2013). The mobility of InnoCampus makes it possible to reach more diverse groups. Mobile Fab Labs have a flexible approach, so they can adapt their curriculum to local people’s level and needs. They provide practice-based and participatory learning for people who do not access training or tools easily.

Figure 18: Details of Turkey's ranking in GEI (Acs, Szerb, & Lloyd, 2018).

Finally, InnoCampus aims to reach a diverse group of people from different backgrounds in the cities it travels to. There is no age limitation or a need to have a technical background to be accepted to its programs. Whereas the initial target participant group was university students and people who had graduated from university, in later stages programs for high school students and children aged 6-12 were also carried out. In 2017, refugees from Syria living in Turkey were also actively invited to InnoCampus programs which resulted in a total participation ratio of 48,3% locals, 42,3% Syrian refugees, and 9,4% other nationalities in 2017.

Refugee entrepreneurship has been a focus of the program starting in 2017 as we see this critical to supporting social integration and the reduction of unemployment. The unemployment rate in local communities where refugees have settled is typically high. Providing traditional and existing jobs to refugees would likely increase the unemployment rate of the local community and increase tensions between the local and refugee communities. The official rate of unemployment among the local youth aged 15 -24 is already quite high at 19% (TÜİK, 2018). InnoCampus aims to contribute a solution to unemployment among youth, and it supports qualified refugees while creating diversity in the training program. Refugees have increasing needs while they stay longer in the host country for education, employment, and vocational training. When these needs are not met, their integration process can be uncertain. When refugee entrepreneurs learn to use tools in Fab Labs, they can have more control on the product they sell (van Holm, 2015). When they have a successful product on the market, they also have potential to create more jobs in their community. Local and refugee teams work together and collaborate within the InnoCampus program. This serves as another opportunity for refugees to integrate to the local community and learn the local language. Two of the refugee entrepreneurs in Gaziantep stated that the InnoCampus Startup Weekend was the first time in 4 years they had a meaningful interaction with Turks since they had moved to Turkey. This interaction benefits both sides as the local entrepreneurs improved their use of Arabic and also English language which was sometimes the only common language for communication in the coworking space. (Figure 19).

In this paper, besides evaluating the program content, methods used, the impact on participants' business and personal development of InnoCampus, we also look at the challenges when organizing programs in different parts of the country with different stakeholders. The conceptual framework used for the evaluation is called "Entrepreneurship Education and Training Programs around World: Dimensions for Success" and is proposed by the World Bank (Valerio, Parton , & Robb, 2014).

Figure 19: Coworking space inside the InnoCampus containers.

2 Methodology

In the methodology part, we presented our research questions which are answered in following sections, the structure of the research method, and findings from interviews with entrepreneurs and InnoCampus' team's reports. The feedback and reports are analyzed based on the conceptual framework which is detailed in 3.2 (Valerio, Parton , & Robb, 2014).

2.1 Method

The conceptual framework from the World Bank's research of "Entrepreneurship Education and Training Programs around World: Dimensions for Success" is used to evaluate outcomes of entrepreneurship education and training. The framework has 4 main components which are program characteristics, participants, context and outcomes (Figure 20) (Valerio, Parton , & Robb, 2014).

Figure 20: World Bank’s Conceptual Framework for evaluations of entrepreneurship training program (Valerio, Parton, & Robb, 2014).

Program characteristics help us compare the InnoCampus program to alternatives and its impact on the participants. We look at the program curriculum and how it’s organized, the level and approach of the InnoCampus team, trainers and mentors, and how the Fab Lab supports the participants. The diversity is an important element of the InnoCampus program because it supports collaborative and multidisciplinary atmosphere while it builds social and cultural skills of entrepreneurs. For this reason, entrepreneurs’ demographic data is analyzed to understand how the participant diversity in terms of gender, nationality, and background. Due to the program’s mobile nature, InnoCampus team faces may face challenges in different cities. The team prepares reports on both the challenges and the counter actions they take to make improvements in future programs.

Research question	Data Collection	Data Evaluation Domains in Conceptual Framework
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which characteristics of the mobile startup accelerator and Fab Lab program differentiate it from other training programs? What is the main impact of the mobile startup accelerator and Fab Lab program on entrepreneurs? 	Interview with program participants	Program characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization of the program How it is delivered by the trainers and the InnoCampus team Content and curriculum Additional services (mentorship, Fab Lab)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How diverse is the program? Why is this important? 	Participant demographic information	Participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The diversity of gender and nationality Multidisciplinary background
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the main challenges of the program? Which of these are due to mobility? What are the main challenges of having refugee in the program? What lessons are learned in each specific city? 	InnoCampus team report	Context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The relationship with stakeholders Economic conditions Cultural constraints and effects
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In which areas can a mobile startup accelerator and Fab Lab program support startups? Which skills does the program help build in participants? 	Interview with program participants	Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changes and development in entrepreneurs’ mindset and their capabilities Status and performance of startups teams

Table 6: The link between research questions and data collection and evaluation process.

To present a model for a successful example of a mobile startup and Fab Lab training program, we have the research questions on Table 1 and use these to guide us through the evaluation. Using the interviews,

their mindset, capabilities, business development and entrepreneurial journey of the program participants are evaluated to measure the impact of InnoCampus program (Table 6).

2.2 Program Characteristics

In this section, we present how we organize the InnoCampus program in each new city including building local partnerships, reaching applicants, the application and selection processes, and trainer selection. Then, we evaluate the content and curriculum of the program, methods used, and the impact of the program on the participants based on the interviews.

The mobility of InnoCampus requires new partnerships with different local stakeholders in each city. Typical stakeholders include municipalities, Technology Transfer Offices (TTO), universities, local and international NGOs, chambers of commerce and industry, SMEs and local startups. Each city has its unique dynamics based on the local industry, agriculture, culture, and education level. InnoCampus prefers to set up the container structure on the campus of the largest university in the relevant city due to logistical advantages and ease of access to academic and student entrepreneurs and makers. The university and sometimes the TTO help with finding the best location on campus and the announcement of the program. The chambers of commerce and industry in each city may provide mentors to relevant startup teams in the program, help with setting up visits to local companies if needed, and sometimes provide sponsorships as well. NGOs can help with reaching out to the refugee community in the city and finding the appropriate candidates for the program within this community.

The application and selection process varies according to the level of startups in the relevant city. InnoCampus accepts early stages startups who have already started working on their business ideas and who preferably have prototypes of their product. In the selection process, candidates apply first to the program by filling out the form on the website. In the application form, entrepreneurs answer questions about their education level, project idea, team, prototype, interest in Fab Lab, and expectations from the program. InnoCampus team first selects the teams for face-to-face and phone interviews based on the specific selection criteria related to the level of their business idea, the team, their progress so far.

The best teams are then invited to a Startup Weekend where they work for 48 hours on their ideas with the support of mentors. At the end of this event, the teams pitch their ideas to a jury which select 10-15 teams to participate in the 9-week startup accelerator and Fab Lab program at the end of which they pitch their business ideas to a jury and investors at the demo day.

InnoCampus has a 90+ hour syllabus which is divided into three parts: 1. How to Think, 2. How to Make, and 3. How to Sell. The trainings are given by subject matter experts. Each team is assigned to mentors who support them as they develop their business ideas throughout the program.

This paper also studies the results of qualitative interviews carried out with 84 program participants where we focused on three main categories which are building new skills, business development and evaluation of the program. For building new skills, the participants mentioned they had developed more than 10 new skills including soft, entrepreneurial, and tech skills out of which prototyping skill associated with our Fab Lab training was the third most common one.

Participants' answers show that InnoCampus training contributed to their business development most by helping create an entrepreneurial mindset followed closely by helping turn an idea into a business. While some of the teams developed their businesses in specific areas such as marketing, sales, and finance, others found mentorship, collaboration, soft skills they built, working discipline and courage to take action more useful. InnoCampus Startup Accelerator Program supported the startups' business development differently based on the startup idea and how advanced the teams were. Some of the participants also mentioned that Fab Lab training and prototyping opportunity in a startup accelerator program supported them in both building new skills and also their startup's business development. Fab Lab training is found to be the second most useful training after finance training by the program participants. Entrepreneurs also indicated that the Fab Lab is one significant difference InnoCampus program provides compared to other startup programs and it supported them in their entrepreneurial journey.

For the evaluation of the program, the participants answered the following questions:

1. What parts of the InnoCampus program developed you most?

2. Is InnoCampus different from other startup trainings? If so, what is the difference?
3. What was the most useful training and/or workshop?
4. What was the least useful training and/or workshop?

For the first question, the participants answered that the InnoCampus team, mentors and trainers, the general atmosphere, and the program’s content all contributed to their development.

The area which the participants thought they developed the most throughout the program was their communication (15,5%) and their general entrepreneurial mindset (15,5%). Figure 6 shows the areas where the participants believed they improved throughout the InnoCampus program.

Figure 21: Answers to “What parts of the InnoCampus program developed you most?”.

In their answers to the second question, the participants claimed InnoCampus offers a very different style compared to other entrepreneurship trainings and to the education they experienced in the school or university. The welcoming atmosphere and the approach of the InnoCampus team (21,3%) was the determining factor here. An environment with free self-expression and interactive, practice-based training along with the level of collaboration, mentorship and feedback are other mentioned differences (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Answers to the question of “Is InnoCampus different from other startup training? If so, what is the difference?”

The goal of asking about the most useful training was to find a correlation between the specific trainings and the program’s contribution to the participants. Finance (14,9%) training was found the most useful,

and the reason may be a need for investment and management of money for entrepreneurs for their businesses. Fab Lab trainings (13,9%) was found to be the second most useful. Presentation skills and creative communication (10,9%) trainings were also found very useful and this finding supports the observed contribution of the program to the communication skill (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Answers to “Which was the most useful training and/or workshop?”.

The aim of getting feedback about the least useful training is general quality control and to see if there is one with a consistently high ratio. Until now, there were none.

2.3 Participants

The conceptual framework used in this paper evaluates the participants according to their gender, age, education, experience, interests, and behavior (Valerio, Parton, & Robb, 2014). In this section, we look at the participants’ demographic information including gender, background, and nationality to measure the level of diversity.

InnoCampus started organizing startup accelerator and Fab Lab programs in 2015. Since then, a total of 263 entrepreneurs attended the program. 65 % of the participants were male and 35 % of them were female.

In 2017, InnoCampus organized 3 startup accelerator and Fab Lab programs which accepted both refugee and local entrepreneurs in the cities of Gaziantep, Izmir, and Sanliurfa. There was a total of 84 participants (29 in Gaziantep, 23 in Izmir and 32 in Sanliurfa). In this research, we evaluated the data of the participants from these 3 cities.

There were 59 (70,2%) male and 25 (29,8%) female entrepreneurs in 3 InnoCampus startup accelerator and Fab Lab programs. Women entrepreneurship is always one of the priorities of InnoCampus in the selection process. However, having a high number of woman participants is not always possible. In Izmir, participants were accepted from different cities because it was a shorter and more intense program with accommodation. Most of the participants were from more economically developed cities in Turkey which possibly caused relatively higher level of woman participation in Izmir compared to economically less developed cities of Gaziantep and Sanliurfa.

Our goal was to have an equal number of local and refugee participants. However, this was also not always possible as the applications were judged strictly according to the selection criteria. In Izmir, besides refugees from Syria, there were also other nationalities including Palestinian, Iranian, and Egyptian. In Izmir, the low number of refugee participation was due to the low number of refugees in this city and travel restriction of some refugees between cities. While there is a refugee population of around 475,800 in Sanliurfa (Ministry of Interior Directorate General, 2018)), lower education levels and general lack of concrete business ideas from refugee applicants kept the number of refugee participants from being higher (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Gender distribution according to nationalities in cities.

InnoCampus aims to build a multidisciplinary working environment for entrepreneurs for more effective collaboration. In Gaziantep and Sanliurfa, there was a significant difference between entrepreneurs from a technical background and social background, while in Izmir there is almost equal distribution between technical and social occupations. The engineer entrepreneurs mostly are software and electronic engineers (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Background of participants.

2.4 Context

InnoCampus team reported challenges they faced and the lessons learned in each city program, so they could take these into consideration before starting the next program. In addition to reports of the team, program participants also gave suggestions to the program’s content, awards, space, and mentoring which are all taking into consideration to improve the (Table 7).

The conceptual framework includes context which helps us evaluate challenges and changes under economic, political and cultural effects. Economic context affects entrepreneurship in terms of local economic conditions such as the investment climate, specific market opportunities, access to market and regulations. Stability and entrepreneurship promotion are part of the political context. In different societies, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship training can face cultural constraints such as attitudes toward failure or success, traditional roles and local perception (Valerio, Parton , & Robb, 2014).

InnoCampus faced challenges about local partnerships, participant applications, the Fab Lab in general, content, communication, and organization. InnoCampus team reported 60 challenges and what actions they took after each challenge in a year.

There is a need to establish partnerships with local institutions in each new city. Challenges related to these stakeholders, which can be placed under political and cultural context, included were generally related to their limited support, their bias about working with refugees and unfamiliarity of InnoCampus in the new city. Another major challenge was related to communication as most of the refugees are not fluent in Turkish. We overcame this challenge partially by making sure there were English speaking team

members in each team and having an Arabic translator available. Most of the trainers delivered their training both in Turkish and English as we preferred the participants listening to the trainings first hand rather than through a translator if possible. This also increased the level of interaction. A side benefit was the Turkish participants improving their English skills. Another challenge in communication was reaching entrepreneurs and collecting enough applications. We announced the programs in a local newspaper in the 2nd and 3rd city to reach more local entrepreneurs, and Fab Lab workshops weekly to prevent entrepreneurs and local university students missing any session. In the cultural context, participants' perception of and attitudes toward entrepreneurship training created challenges as most did not have a proper business plan. Most of the applicants did not even have a proper business idea but had a general interest in entrepreneurship or were after funding. Limited funding and local investment availability and lack of local market for the teams' products fall under the economic context. Some of the refugees also had to drop out of the program because they had to work to make a living and did not have any free time left for the trainings.

Fab Lab is the most revised part of the programs in terms of training, prototyping process, and program organization. Budget and grant is another topic which InnoCampus team made changes from city to city in consideration of feedbacks and suggestion from entrepreneurs. In Gaziantep, funding opportunity was announced later in the program, and the feedback showed us it motivates the teams, so we decided to use this to increase the number of applications and motivate the teams from the beginning. However, sponsors' cancelation of the funding awards in the 2nd city was a motivation killer even though most of the teams' main reason for attending the program was not the awards. Therefore, in the final city, we did not announce any funding opportunity at the start of the program.

Finally, based on the feedback from entrepreneurs on the trainings, more finance trainings and teamwork sessions were added to the curriculum.

Gaziantep (1 st city)	Izmir (2 nd city)		Sanliurfa (3 rd city)		Future Program
Feedback from participants	Program change	Feedback from participants	Program change	Feedback from participants	Planned program change
More mentorship from InnoCampus team needed	Extended mentorship sessions with InnoCampus team organized		Extended mentorship sessions with InnoCampus team organized	More time with a dedicated mentor	More time with dedicated mentor for each team
The announcement of funding earlier	Funding was announced earlier				
Networking with previous graduates and similar entrepreneurship institutions	Graduates day for networking				2 nd graduates day planned in Summer 2018
More teamwork time	Free day in containers for team work and collaboration	Training too intense, no time left for teamwork	More teamwork sessions after training		
		More finance training	Finance trainings as of 1 st week		
More Fab Lab workshops	Extended Fab Lab Program for a week				

Gaziantep (1 st city)	Izmir (2 nd city)		Sanliurfa (3 rd city)		Future Program
Feedback from participants	Program change	Feedback from participants	Program change	Feedback from participants	Planned program change
		Tech-savvy mentors needed	Tech-savvy mentors invited to the program		

Table 7: Feedback from program participants and how the InnoCampus program was modified accordingly.

2.5 Outcomes

The conceptual framework has 4 parameters for evaluation of outcomes which are entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial capabilities which entrepreneurs build during the program, status which includes starting a business, and finally performance which may include higher profits and increased sales (Valerio, Parton, & Robb, 2014).

In the evaluation of InnoCampus' participants, to evaluate entrepreneurial mindset and capabilities, we collected data about new skills building and business development. To evaluate status, we collected data on their entrepreneurial journey. Since InnoCampus accepts early-stage startups which are not in the market yet, there is no such data on business performance. To measure performance, we evaluated the teams' business development.

Figure 26: Entrepreneurs' new skills built in the program.

In the interviews, we asked the participants whether InnoCampus had an influence on developing their skills and if so, how. Then, we categorized their answers under 15 different skills. The participants claimed they developed a new mindset (21,6%) which means entrepreneurs gained a new perspective about specific topics and their awareness about entrepreneurship increased. Presentation skills are one of the key skills for entrepreneurs when they interact with both customers and investors. 20,3% of the participants said they developed themselves in presentation skills, 13,5% in Fab Lab skills, and 8,1% in self-expression (Figure 26).

Finally, the interviewees were asked how InnoCampus made a difference in their entrepreneurial journey and how the training and workshops in InnoCampus contributed to the development of their business idea. 23,5% of the feedback indicates that bring their idea to a business contributed their entrepreneurial journey the most. 21,3% of the feedback shows that training in business subject

develop the businesses the most, while entrepreneurial mindset (16,9%) and personal development (8,1%) have also a significant contribution to their business and entrepreneurial journey (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Impact of InnoCampus on entrepreneurship' business development.

3 Conclusion

InnoCampus creates an accessible model in entrepreneurship and Fab Lab training which can travel different geographies to support local entrepreneurs and makers. The curriculum of a mobile program should be flexible to adapt to local condition and varying needs in different cities. One key factor affecting the success of such a program the level of cooperation with local stakeholders which affect the promotion of the program and reaching the right candidates to the simplest meeting of logistic needs.

Participants of the InnoCampus program claimed the program contributed to their business development most by helping create an entrepreneurial mindset followed closely by helping turn an idea into a business. While some of the teams developed their businesses in specific areas such as marketing, sales, and finance, others found mentorship, collaboration, soft skills they built, working discipline and courage to take action more useful. InnoCampus Startup Accelerator Program supported the startups' business development differently based on the startup idea and how advanced the teams were. Some of the participants also mentioned that Fab Lab training and prototyping opportunity in a startup accelerator program supported them in both building new skills and also their startup's business development. Fab Lab training is found to be the second most useful training after finance training by the program participants. Entrepreneurs also indicated that the Fab Lab is one significant difference InnoCampus program provides compared to other startup programs and it supported them in their entrepreneurial journey.

The mobility of InnoCampus made its entrepreneurship and Fab Lab training, prototyping opportunity, and collaborative working environment accessible to locals and refugees in different geographies. Entrepreneurs not only developed their business idea along with new skills, they also supported each other, learned, worked, and created together.

Including refugee entrepreneurs in the InnoCampus Program supported social cohesion between local and refugee participants as the teams collaborated. They worked together to bring their business ideas to life and they supported each other by giving feedback or helping with their expertise. Starting their own businesses also has great potential to support refugees' economic independence and improve their overall morale.

Since InnoCampus accepts early-stage startups, following their progress after the program and evaluation of program's impact in further stages of their entrepreneurial journey will be the subject of our next research.

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